

LARGE AMPLITUDE VIBRATION OF GEOMETRICALLY IMPERFECT
SYMMETRICALLY LAMINATED SHALLOW SPHERICAL SHELL
WITH ELASTICALLY RESTRAINED EDGES

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ABSTRACT

A multi-mode solution to the dynamic Marguerre-type nonlinear equations is formulated for the titled problem with the shell edges on a rectangular base under tangential forces. The transverse displacement and a force function used in these equations are expressed in the form of generalized double Fourier series with time-dependent coefficients. These series satisfy the boundary conditions for opposite edges elastically restrained against rotation to the same degree. These equations thus are orthogonalized with respect to orthogonal functions in these series. The resulting equations for time-dependent coefficients are solved by the method of harmonic balance. The nonlinear vibration of symmetric cross-ply rectangular plates under inplane forces can be treated as a special case. Using a one-term approximation for the transverse displacement, numerical results for the amplitude-frequency response of symmetric cross-ply shallow spherical square shells are presented graphically for various values of geometrical imperfection and rotational edge stiffness.

INTRODUCTION

Nonlinear flexural vibrations of flat plates have been investigated extensively. Results in the amplitude-frequency response of curved panels and shallow shells, however, are less comprehensive. On the basis of von Karman-type equations and the Galerkin method the nonlinear vibration of a shallow cylindrical panel was discussed by Cummings [1] for the isotropic case and by Ramachandran and Murthy [2] for the orthotropic case. Assuming constant mid-surface stresses in the arc direction and the vanishing of the other stresses, Massalas and Kafousias [3] studied the large amplitude vibration of a shallow cylindrical isotropic panel on a

nonlinear elastic foundation. Utilizing Donnell-type nonlinear equations Hui [4] applied the Galerkin technique to the dynamic problem of an imperfect cylindrical isotropic panel. The nonlinear free vibration of an imperfect symmetric cross-ply shallow cylindrical panel with two adjacent edges simply supported and the other edges clamped was treated by the writer [5] using a one-term approximation. In addition to the references listed in [6] several authors [7 - 9] also studied the amplitude-frequency response of spherical caps. In the case of nonlinear vibration of perfect shallow shells on a rectangular base, a single-mode analysis was carried out by Leissa and Kadi [10] using the Galerkin procedure for simply supported edges.

The present paper deals with the influences of composite material properties, geometry of lamination, rotational edge stiffness, geometrically initial imperfection and tangential edge force on the large-amplitude flexural free vibration of a symmetrically laminated shallow spherical shell with a rectangular boundary. The rotational stiffness is assumed identical along opposite edges. The four edges are free from stresses. As shown in [10] the effect of the tangential inertia on frequencies of various modes of vibration of a shallow spherical shell on a square base is less than one percent and hence the effect is neglected in this work.

GOVERNING EQUATIONS

Consider a shallow spherical shell of midsurface radius R and thickness h on a rectangular base with boundary length a in the x -direction and width b in the y -direction. The shell is assumed to consist of n layers of unidirectional orthotropic sheets perfectly bonded together. Each layer has arbitrary thickness, elastic properties, and orientation of orthotropic axes with respect to the plate axes. However, the layers are so arranged that a midsurface symmetry exists. Including the initial curvature of the shell in equations (2-167) of page 98 in Ref. [11] and following the derivation for equations (1-153) and (1-154) of page 35 in [11], the dynamic Marguerre-type equations are obtained. Ignoring the tangential and rotatory inertia effects [10], these basic equations governing the nonlinear free flexural vibration of the shell of geometrically initial imperfections in the sense of von Karman may be expressed in the following nondimensional form:

$$\begin{aligned}
& W_{,\zeta\zeta\zeta\zeta} + a_1 \lambda W_{,\zeta\zeta\zeta\eta} + 2a_2 \lambda^2 W_{,\zeta\zeta\eta\eta} + a_3 \lambda^3 W_{,\zeta\eta\eta\eta} + a_4 \lambda^4 W_{,\eta\eta\eta\eta} \\
& + \lambda^4 W_{,\tau\tau} / \bar{D}_{11} - (\lambda^2 / \bar{D}_{11}) [F_{,\zeta\zeta} (K + W_{,\eta\eta} + \bar{w}_{,\eta\eta}) \\
& + F_{,\eta\eta} (K + W_{,\zeta\zeta} + \bar{w}_{,\zeta\zeta}) - 2F_{,\zeta\eta} (W_{,\zeta\eta} + \bar{w}_{,\zeta\eta})] = 0 \quad (1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& F_{,\zeta\zeta\zeta\zeta} - b_1 \lambda F_{,\zeta\zeta\zeta\eta} + 2b_2 \lambda^2 F_{,\zeta\zeta\eta\eta} - b_3 \lambda^3 F_{,\zeta\eta\eta\eta} + b_4 \lambda^4 F_{,\eta\eta\eta\eta} \\
& = (\lambda^2 / \bar{A}_{22}) [W_{,\zeta\eta}^2 - W_{,\zeta\zeta} (K + \bar{w}_{,\eta\eta}) - W_{,\eta\eta} (K + W_{,\zeta\zeta} + \bar{w}_{,\zeta\zeta}) \\
& + 2W_{,\zeta\eta} \bar{w}_{,\zeta\eta}] \quad (2)
\end{aligned}$$

in which the subscripts preceded by a comma denote differentiation with respect to the corresponding coordinates and coefficients a_i , b_i , \bar{D}_{11} and \bar{A}_{22} are constants of the shell given by the corresponding coefficients in equations (5-201) and (5-202) of page 270 in Ref. [11] and in which

$$\begin{aligned}
\zeta &= \frac{x}{a}, \quad \eta = \frac{y}{b}, \quad \tau = \frac{t}{2} \sqrt{\frac{A_{22} h^2}{\rho}}, \quad W = \frac{w}{h} \\
\bar{w} &= \frac{\bar{w}}{h}, \quad F = \frac{\psi}{A_{22} h^2}, \quad \lambda = \frac{a}{b}, \quad K = \frac{b^2}{Rh} \quad (3)
\end{aligned}$$

In these expressions w is the deflection, \bar{w} is the initial deflection, ψ is the force function, t is the time, ρ is the shell mass per unit area, and A_{22} is the membrane rigidity of the shell in the y -direction.

In this work the shell is assumed to be rigidly supported against the transverse displacement and opposite edges are restrained against rotation to the same degree. The shell is subjected to biaxial edge forces per unit length, \bar{N}_x in the x -direction and \bar{N}_y in the y -direction, but not the boundary shearing forces. These boundary conditions for a symmetrically laminated cross-ply shell ($a_1 = a_3 = b_1 = b_3 = 0$) may be written in the nondimensional form as

$$\begin{aligned}
W &= 0, \quad W_{,\zeta\zeta} = \pm \xi_1 W_{,\zeta}, \quad F_{,\eta\eta} = \bar{N}_\zeta, \quad F_{,\zeta\eta} = 0 \quad \text{at } \zeta = 0, 1 \\
W &= 0, \quad W_{,\eta\eta} = \pm \xi_2 W_{,\eta}, \quad F_{,\zeta\zeta} = \lambda^2 r \bar{N}_\zeta, \quad F_{,\zeta\eta} = 0 \quad \text{at } \eta = 0, 1
\end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where ξ_i are nondimensional parameters in rotationally restrained coefficients along the shell edges and where

$$\bar{N}_\zeta = \bar{N}_x b^2 / A_{22} h^2, \quad r = \bar{N}_y / \bar{N}_x \quad (5)$$

METHOD OF SOLUTION

A solution to equations (1) and (2) is sought in the separable form

$$W = \sum_{m,n=1}^{\infty} W_{mn}(\tau) \phi_m(\zeta) \psi_n(\eta) \quad (6)$$

$$\bar{W} = \sum_{m,n=1}^{\infty} \bar{W}_{mn} \phi_m(\zeta) \psi_n(\eta) \quad (7)$$

$$F = \frac{1}{2} \bar{N}_\zeta (\eta^2 + r \zeta^2) + \sum_{p,q=1}^{\infty} F_{pq}(\tau) X_p(\zeta) Y_q(\eta) \quad (8)$$

where ϕ_m , ψ_n , X_m and Y_n are beam eigenfunctions given by

$$\phi_m(\zeta) = A_m (\cosh \alpha_m \zeta - \cos \alpha_m \zeta) + B_m \sinh \alpha_m \zeta + \sin \alpha_m \zeta \quad (9)$$

$$\psi_n(\eta) = A_n (\cosh \alpha_n \eta - \cos \alpha_n \eta) + B_n \sinh \alpha_n \eta + \sin \alpha_n \eta$$

and

$$X_p(\zeta) = \cosh \beta_p \zeta - \cos \beta_p \zeta - \gamma_p (\sinh \beta_p \zeta - \sin \beta_p \zeta) \quad (10)$$

$$Y_q(\eta) = \cosh \beta_q \eta - \cos \beta_q \eta - \gamma_q (\sinh \beta_q \eta - \sin \beta_q \eta)$$

Introduction of series (6) and (8) for W and F in boundary conditions (4) results in the values of A_i , B_i and α_i (not presented herein). The inplane edge conditions in equations (4) are satisfied if the values of β_i and γ_i are taken from Table 1. Functions $\phi_i(\zeta)$, $\psi_i(\eta)$ and $X_i(\zeta)$ and $Y_i(\eta)$

TABLE 1

Values of β_k and γ_k in equations (10)

k	β_k	γ_k
1	4.7300407448627	0.98250221457624
2	7.8532046240958	1.00077731190727
3	10.9956078380017	0.99996645012541
4	14.1371654912575	0.00000144989766
5	17.2787596573994	0.99999993734439
>5	$(2k + 1)\pi/2$	1.00000000000000

possess the following orthogonality relations:

$$\int_0^1 \phi_i \phi_j \, d\zeta = \int_0^1 \psi_i \psi_j \, d\eta = \begin{cases} 0 & , \quad i \neq j \\ H_i & , \quad i = j \end{cases}$$

$$\int_0^1 X_i X_j \, d\zeta = \int_0^1 Y_i Y_j \, d\eta = \begin{cases} 0 & , \quad i \neq j \\ 1 & , \quad i = j \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

where

$$H_i = \frac{1}{2}(2A_i^2 - B_i^2 + 1) + \frac{A_i}{\alpha_i} (B_i + 1) \quad (12)$$

Substituting series expansions (6) - (8) for W , \bar{W} and F in governing equations (1) and (2), multiplying the first of the resulting equations by $\phi_i(\zeta)\psi_j(\eta)$ and the second by $X_i(\zeta)Y_j(\eta)$, integrating with respect to ζ and η from 0 to 1, and using the orthogonality properties (11) we obtain the following equations for the coefficients $W_{ij}(\tau)$ and $F_{ij}(\tau)$:

$$\begin{aligned} & (\beta_i^4 + b_4 \beta_j^4) F_{ij}(\tau) + 2b_2 \sum_p \sum_q K_1^{ip} L_1^{jq} F_{pq}(\tau) \\ & = \frac{1}{\bar{A}_{22}} \sum_m \sum_n W_{mn}(\tau) \{ \sum_p \sum_q W_{pq}(\tau) [K_2^{imp} L_2^{jqn} - K_3^{imp} L_3^{jqn}] \\ & - \sum_p \sum_q \bar{W}_{pq} [K_3^{imp} L_3^{jqn} + K_3^{ipm} L_3^{jqn} - 2K_2^{imp} L_2^{jqn}] \\ & - K(K_4^{im} L_5^{jn} + K_5^{im} L_4^{jn}) \} \quad i, j = 1, 2, 3, \dots \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

$$\begin{aligned} & W_{ij, \tau\tau} + \bar{D}_{11} (\alpha_i^4 + a_4 \alpha_j^4) W_{ij}(\tau) + 2a_2 \bar{D}_{11} \\ & \cdot (H_i H_j)^{-1} \sum_n \sum_m K_6^{im} L_6^{jn} W_{mn}(\tau) = (H_i H_j)^{-1} \{ K \bar{N}_\zeta (1 + r) \\ & \cdot K_7^{ij} L_7^j + \bar{N}_\zeta H_j \sum_m K_6^{im} [\bar{W}_{mj} + W_{mj}(\tau)] \\ & + r \bar{N}_\zeta H_i \sum_n L_6^{jn} [\bar{W}_{in} + W_{in}(\tau)] + K \sum_p \sum_q F_{pq}(\tau) \\ & \cdot [K_4^{pi} L_8^{jq} + K_8^{ip} L_4^{qj}] + \sum_m \sum_n \sum_p \sum_q (K_3^{pmi} L_9^{jnq} \\ & + K_9^{imp} L_3^{qnj} - 2K_{10}^{imp} L_{10}^{jnq}) F_{pq}(\tau) [\bar{W}_{mn} + W_{mn}(\tau)] \} \\ & i, j = 1, 2, 3, \dots \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

where K_i 's and L 's are definite integrals but not presented here.

Equations (13) can be solved for $F_{ij}(\tau)$ in terms of $W_{mn}(\tau)$. On substitution equations (14) reduce to a set of nonlinear ordinary differential equations for $W_{mn}(\tau)$ only. These equations can be solved by the method of harmonic balance. To simplify numerical calculations a single-mode approach is adopted for the rest of this work by replacing in equations (6)-(8)

$$\sum_m \sum_n W_{mn}(\tau) \text{ by } cf(\tau), \quad \sum_m \sum_n \bar{W}_{mn} \text{ by } c\bar{W}_0, \text{ and}$$

$$F_{pq}(\tau) \text{ by } [I_{pq} f^2(\tau) + J_{pq} f(\tau)] \quad \text{where } c = [\phi_m(\zeta_1)\psi_n(\eta_1)]^{-1} \quad (15)$$

and where \bar{W}_0 is the ratio of the amplitude of initial imperfection to the shell thickness, and ζ_1 and η_1 are coordinates of the location at which the amplitude of vibration, w_{\max} , occurs. It is observed that the foregoing simplified solution for series (6)-(8) also satisfies all boundary conditions.

Inserting expressions (15) in equations (13) and equating coefficients of $f^2(\tau)$ and $f(\tau)$ respectively, we obtain two independent sets of linear algebraic equations, one set for I_{pq} and the other for J_{pq} .

$$\begin{aligned} I_{ij}(\beta_i^4 + b_4\beta_j^4) + 2b_2 \sum_p \sum_q I_{pq} K_1^{ip} L_1^{jq} \\ = (c^2/\bar{A}_{22})(K_2^{imm} L_2^{jnn} - K_3^{imm} L_3^{jnn}) \quad i, j = 1, 2, 3, \dots \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

$$\begin{aligned} J_{ij}(\beta_i^4 + b_4\beta_j^4) + 2b_2 \sum_p \sum_q J_{pq} K_1^{ip} L_1^{jq} \\ = -(c/\bar{A}_{22}) [2c\bar{W}_0 (K_3^{imm} L_3^{jnn} - K_2^{imm} L_2^{jnn}) \\ + K(K_4^{im} L_5^{jn} + K_5^{im} L_4^{jn})] \quad i, j = 1, 2, 3, \dots \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

For the one-term approximation equations (14) reduce to a differential equation for the time-dependent function $f(\tau)$ as follows:

$$f_{,\tau\tau} + (\delta_1 - \delta_2 \bar{N}_\zeta) f + \epsilon_1 f^2 + \epsilon_2 f^3 = \delta_3 \bar{N}_\zeta \quad (18)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}
\delta_1 &= \bar{D}_{11} (\alpha_m^4 + a_4 \alpha_n^4) + (\bar{D}_{11}/H_m H_n) \{ 2a_2 K_6^{mm} L_6^{nn} \\
&\quad - \sum_p \sum_q J_{pq} [(K/c) (K_4^{mp} L_8^{nq} + K_8^{mp} L_4^{qn}) \\
&\quad - \bar{W}_0 (2K_{10}^{mmp} L_{10}^{nnq} - K_3^{pmm} L_9^{nnq} - K_9^{mmp} L_3^{qnn})] \} \\
\delta_2 &= (H_n K_6^{mm} + r H_m L_6^{nn}) / (H_m H_n) \\
\epsilon_1 &= \frac{1}{c H_m H_n} \sum_p \sum_q [c (I_{pq} \bar{W}_0 + J_{pq}) (2K_{10}^{mmp} L_{10}^{nnq} \\
&\quad - K_3^{pmm} L_9^{nnq} - K_9^{mmp} L_3^{qnn}) - K I_{pq} (K_4^{mp} L_8^{nq} + K_8^{mp} L_4^{qn})] \quad (19) \\
\epsilon_2 &= \frac{1}{H_m H_n} \sum_p \sum_q I_{pq} (2K_{10}^{mmp} L_{10}^{nnq} - K_3^{pmm} L_9^{nnq} - K_9^{mmp} L_3^{qnn}) \\
\delta_3 &= \frac{1}{c H_m H_n} [K(1+r) K_7^{mn} + c \bar{W}_0 (H_n K_6^{mm} + r H_m L_6^{nn})]
\end{aligned}$$

For a harmonic motion of geometrically imperfect symmetric cross-ply shallow spherical shells we take $\bar{N}_\zeta = 0$ in equation (18). In the case of nonlinear vibration of symmetric cross-ply flat plates under inplane forces we take $K = \bar{W}_0 = 0$ in this equation. The linear frequency $\omega_{mn}^{(o)}$ of the (m,n) mode of vibration is related to the linear frequency parameter ω_o by

$$\omega_o = b^2 (\rho/A_{22} h^2)^{\frac{1}{2}} \omega_{mn}^{(o)} = (\delta_1 - \delta_2 \bar{N}_\zeta)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (20)$$

An approximate solution of equation (18) can be obtained by the perturbation method. For a more accurate solution the method of harmonic balance is used with the time function $f(\tau)$ represented by

$$f(\tau) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} f_k \cos k\omega\tau \quad (21)$$

in which f_k is the k th harmonic amplitude and ω is the nondimensional nonlinear frequency similarly defined as ω_o by equation (20). The assumed solution for $f(\tau)$ is inserted in equation (18) and each cosine function is converted into the first power of cosine function. Equating the coefficients of like cosine terms to zero, a system of simultaneous nonlinear algebraic equations is obtained. This tedious task can be handled systematically by a computer for an arbitrary number of terms in the truncated series (21).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Computations were performed for shallow spherical square shells which consist of odd number of thin orthotropic pliers all of the same thickness. Elastic constants typical of glass-epoxy and boron-epoxy materials are given in Table 2 where E_L and E_T are principal moduli of elasticity of an

TABLE 2

Numerical values of elastic constants

Material	E_L/E_T	G_{LT}/E_T	ν_{LT}
Glass-epoxy	3	0.6	0.25
Boron-epoxy	10	1/3	0.22

orthotropic material, G_{LT} is the shear modulus and ν_{LT} is Poisson's ratio. The first sixteen and eight terms in truncated series (8) and (21) are respectively taken into account. Numerical results indicate that the harmonic amplitudes in the last four terms are negligibly small compared to those in the first four terms in series (21).

Present results for nonlinear vibration of rectangular plates with all-simply supported and all-clamped stress-free edges are in good agreement with those given by Yamaki [12] for isotropic plates and in fair agreement with those obtained by Prabhakara and Chia [13] using a multi-mode analysis for orthotropic plates. Fundamental linear frequencies of a clamped orthotropic rectangular plate under uniform biaxial edge tension are compared with the available data [14] for different aspect ratios and edge forces. The maximum difference between the two sets of values is less than 1.5 percent. The present amplitude-fundamental frequency response curve for a simply supported shallow spherical isotropic shell on a square boundary for $w_{\max} < 10 h$ is in good agreement with that given by Leissa and Kadi [10]. These results, however, are not presented herein.

The amplitude-frequency response of a cross-ply shell is depicted in Fig. 1 for various values of the rotational edge stiffness coefficient ξ . The results for $\xi = 0, \infty$ correspond to all-simply-supported and all-clamped edges respectively. All these curves exhibit initially a soft-spring behavior and then revert to the hardening type at large amplitudes. As

there are regions where the amplitude is not unique for a given frequency, the jump phenomenon may occur. The influence of the initial transverse displacement on the amplitude-frequency response of a cross-ply shell is illustrated in Fig. 2. Opposite edges at $\zeta = 0, 1$ are simply supported and the other edges are clamped. The result for $\bar{W}_0 = 1$ corresponds to the amplitude of initial imperfection equal to the shell thickness. All these curves possess a similar behavior to those in Fig. 1. The initial

Figure 1. Effect of rotational edge stiffness on fundamental nonlinear frequency of a perfect three-layer cross-ply boron-epoxy shallow spherical square shell ($K = 25$).

Figure 2. Effect of geometrical imperfections on fundamental nonlinear frequency of simply supported-clamped five-layer cross-ply glass-epoxy shallow spherical square shell ($K = 80$).

imperfection reduces the degree of nonlinearity at small finite amplitudes and the degree of the softening-type behavior.

$$\bar{E} = \frac{3}{8} E_1 + \frac{5}{8} E_2$$

↑
along equator

CONCLUSIONS

A multi-mode solution to the dynamic Marguerre-type nonlinear equations is formulated for nonlinear vibration of an imperfect symmetric cross-ply shallow spherical shell on a rectangular boundary. Based on a single-mode approximation numerical results are presented graphically for various values of rotational edge stiffness and initial deflection. Acknowledgement - The results presented in this paper were obtained in the course of research sponsored by the Natural Science and Engineering Research Council of Canada.

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